

PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING MEDIA LITERACY IN PRIMARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article discusses the meaning and essence of the concepts of "media", "literacy", "media literacy", and the fact that it is a pedagogical necessity to develop media literacy among students.

Key words: media, literacy, media literacy, mass media, media education, media competence, primary education.

Introduction:

Important steps have been taken to improve the information services system in our country in recent years. Thanks to the Internet, news can travel around the world at the speed of light, and so can lies, conspiracy theories, and misinformation. Lies on the Internet can be harmful in the real world. While some look to technology regulations to combat the scourge of fake news, the strongest defense is building a strong media literate citizenry. Media literacy is more important now than ever. The simplest definition of media literacy is the ability to access, analyze, evaluate, create, and act on various forms of media. Simply put, media literacy builds on the foundations of traditional literacy and offers new forms of reading and writing. Media literacy enables people to be critical and creative thinkers, effective communicators, and active citizens.

Literature analysis and methods:

In 2005, the "Media education" textbook was created under the auspices of UNESCO, and the website of film education and media pedagogy was launched in Russia. Today, no one denies the power of manipulative influence of the information distributed through mass media. If we look at the history, we can see that the belief in the authenticity of the news spread through the mass media appeared with the appearance of the first newspapers.

Media literacy classes are held in journalism faculties and departments of universities of the republic, such as the University of Journalism and Mass Communications of Uzbekistan, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, National University of Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan State University of World Languages, Karshi State University, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the word literacy is defined as a person who knows how to read, write, and is literate.

Literacy can be defined as the ability to identify, interpret, understand and communicate. Literacy skills include the ability to read, write, speak and listen effectively.

The term media comes from the Latin "medium", which means "tool", "mediator", "method" and means the concept of communication and information media in various forms. More precisely, it means "mass media". This term has several meanings in modern usage.

- ❖ **First**, the word "media" means "mass media", means radio, book, television, newspaper, internet.
- ❖ **Second**, it is used to mark media content - news, advertising, announcements, electronic games and movies.
- ❖ **Third**, it can also refer to media content producers, journalists, photographers, media companies, and others¹.

Different opinions have been expressed about media literacy. It goes hand in hand with issues that form the basis of media education, such as the necessity, purpose and needs of media literacy. Various theoretical and practical approaches regarding the background, development process and current state of media literacy have been put forward by various scientists.

The term "media literacy" is often used interchangeably with other terms related to mass media and media technologies. To clarify what we mean when we talk about media literacy, here are some definitions of media literacy:

- Media means all electronic or digital means and printed or artistic images used to transmit messages.
- Literacy is the ability to encode, decode, synthesize and analyze messages.
- Media literacy is the ability to encode and decode symbols transmitted by mass media and learn to synthesize, analyze, and produce mediated messages.
- Media education is the study of mass media, including "hands-on" experience and media production.

According to Fresno Pacific University, "Media literacy helps students become wise consumers of media as well as responsible producers of their own media. In the same direction, teaching media literacy helps students develop critical thinking. This type of thinking can eventually become second nature to a person, which will help them in many areas as they grow up."

In the classroom, students working on media and news literacy will help them become strong critical thinkers in all aspects of their lives.

Today, the information society poses many problems to the modern university. The Internet and modern technologies not only filled the lack of information, prevented excessive time consumption and became a serious competitor of traditional educational norms. Teachers and students are constantly forced to look for new resources to improve their media competence. The teacher has the task of becoming a "guide" and consultant in the world of information for students. Today, the student simultaneously works as a consumer of information content, information technologies, and as an author, creator of media products. Students' access to the modern information space often happens by itself and does not require much pedagogical support. For example, teaching students the ethical standards of communication, effective search and selection of safe information on the Internet, and teaching them are relevant. Development of students' media literacy should be considered as an important independent educational task in a modern university.

Discussion:

¹ Pedagogical aspects of formation of media and information literacy. Educational and practical manual.-T.: Extremum-press, 2017

Development of media and information skills in students requires advanced media competence. Teachers actively use a multimedia projector in the auditorium (nowadays lectures are rarely given without a presentation), video materials, and an interactive whiteboard. Some teachers have created a social page to communicate and post updates for students. Members of the online community use it for professional development.

As a result of media education, media literacy is not limited to students' mastery of modern information technologies or development of critical information analysis skills. A broader view of the concept of media education is required. In the efficient and quick use of information, the student can determine the type of information needed to solve a specific problem, can access this information efficiently and quickly; identify keywords and relevant terms to access information of interest; can identify different types and formats of potential information sources and do many more things.

Competence of critical assessment of information and information sources. The student is able to critically evaluate information and its sources, and can use selected information to solve problems and analyze ideas, and can analyze the reliability of the source, its accuracy, and accuracy. Media literacy is the ability to convey, interpret, and improve value using mass media. Media Literacy Education is known to help the user become more aware, develop interpretative skills, develop the ability to analyze news correctly, and develop the ability of the viewer to analyze news correctly and have a critical perspective.

The development of information and communication technologies is changing the way people use mass media. Media literacy is increasingly important in today's society because media is primarily created and consumed online. Arming students with the skills needed to be savvy consumers of information will help them build strong digital citizens with the ability to evaluate resources and participate in safe and healthy digital conversations.

Analyze and evaluate using critical thinking. How do students know which source is reliable when faced without the help of a teacher? Whether they are watching YouTube, reading the news, or analyzing images, students need the skills to understand information, put it into context, and distinguish between real and fake. One way to do this is to teach students to ask questions when analyzing and evaluating media. It is also important to give students time and space to think for themselves and teach them how to ask questions so they can learn to analyze and evaluate media independently.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it can be said that as a result of media literacy, students acquire the skills of analyzing and evaluating the quality of information in the educational process in general.

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